

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842
ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

MULTIDISCIPLINARY E-PUBLICATION

Vol. IV Issue VII, July 2024

Monthly Issue

International Circulation

Pinagpala
PUBLISHING SERVICES

NBDB Reg. No. 3269

DTI Business Reg. No. 3034433

TIN 293-150-678/ Business Permit No. 8183

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THE SCIENCE PYRAMID: AN INNOVATIVE STRATEGIC INTERVENTION MATERIAL IN PHYSICS 8

Eduardo B. Ma Jr, LPT

Student

Tarlac State University, Region III

Rita E. Pulmano, Ed.D.

Co-author

Title: **THE SCIENCE PYRAMID: AN INNOVATIVE STRATEGIC
INTERVENTION MATERIAL IN PHYSICS 8**

Main Author: **EDUARDO B. MA JR (jrmaeduardo@gmail.com)**

Institution: **TARLAC STATE UNIVERSITY**

Degree: **MASTER OF ARTS IN EDUCATION**

Major: **PHYSICAL SCIENCE**

Co-author: **RITA E. PULMANO, Ed.D.**

Abstract

This study developed and validated The Science Pyramid or The SciePy, an innovative strategic intervention material in least learned competencies in Physics 8. The researcher used the ADDIE model and the Department of Education's LRMDs Evaluation Tool on Manipulative content, manipulative designs, and error-free factors, which were evaluated by six experts in science education. Thirty-one student-participants, who needed intervention, utilized it during learning sessions and validated its effectiveness based on their pre-test and post-test results.

The findings revealed that The SciePy passed all factors, specifically 38.83 out of 40.00 in content, 16.00 out of 16.00 in error-free issues, and 23.83 out of 24.00 in manipulative designs. Therefore, it was found valid and recommended by validators to be utilized for learning sessions. Eventually, the paired t-test results showed that there was a significant difference in the participants' scores with a significant p-value of <0.001. Thus, there was a remarkable improvement in the participants' scores using The SciePy.

The SciePy can be validated through bigger sample sizes with various backgrounds and academic levels, additional expert validators with the inclusion of educational

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World Education Connect

Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue VII (July 2024), p.21-38 International

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

technologists or instructional designers, and a comparison between the traditional teaching method and the one integrated with it. Secondly, reproducing it could be costly, but using indigenous or recyclable materials like polyvinyl chloride (PVC), bamboo, or any durable lumber could be cost-effective and improve dimensions and features. Finally, it may also be incorporated with different learning competencies from the DepEd's MATATAG Curriculum to further test its efficacy.

Introduction

Science teachers are called for innovation to step up against the challenges of the teachers' creativity and learners' learning styles of today's world (Contreras, 2018). While it is true that there is no perfect way of teaching science, teachers must constantly work to close the gap between their traditional methods of education and emerging innovations by seeking active use of practices that learners need today (Iwuanyanwu, 2019).

Innovation, the action of implementing new ideas and ways to produce new or better value, has existed throughout human history. Humans have always struggled to discover new methods to create value and improve the quality of life through innovation. (Lee, 2018).

Indeed, teachers play a critical role in providing students with the tools they need to rethink strategies for dealing with real-world problems by developing their skills in creativity, positive attitudes toward scientists, and science as a significant factor in the development of society, all of which can be addressed with an arsenal of practical knowledge and rational application. However, science teachers should have access to innovative classrooms, materials, and hands-on experiences, and both the public and private sectors should invest more resources in science education development (Yoldere, Adamu, & Inuwa, 2018).

Unfortunately, no matter how good or innovative a teacher may be, there are always students who need to catch up for various reasons. King'aru (2014) concludes that some schools lack equipment, classrooms are unfit for science lessons, and students have negative attitudes toward science, discouraging them from performing well in science. Nevertheless, they suggest teachers be more innovative in preparing teaching and learning materials and embrace interactive teaching.

Ban, Kim, and Shin (2022) recommend checking which students need to catch up and provide guidance that matches their levels. However, to genuinely enhance science literacy among Filipino students, Bernardo et al. (2023) propose comprehending the challenges faced by those falling short, as these indicate issues that should be resolved in the classroom.

In the Philippines, Republic Act No. 10533, or the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013, paved the way for the development and implementation of the K to 12 curriculum. It aims to foster lifelong learners, provide students with enough time to understand ideas and skills and prepare them for postsecondary education, middle-level skill development, employment, and entrepreneurship (Official Gazette of the Philippines, n.d.). In the curriculum, science education strives to raise scientific literacy in students so that they can make informed judgments about how to use scientific information. It seeks to educate students on functional skills in the workplace and a knowledge-based society. Likewise, it aims to build scientifically, technologically, and ecologically literate and productive citizens who are critical problem solvers, responsible stewards of nature, inventive and creative

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citizens, educated decision-makers, and effective communicators (Department of Education, 2016).

However, despite such substantial educational reform, the Philippines still faced challenges in science education. International large-scale assessments like the Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) revealed the education status and the quality of science education as 15-year-old students scored lower in science than those in most participating countries and economies with a score of 357 while the average is 487. Thus, for first-time participation, the Philippines ranked 78th out of 79 partaking nations (Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development, 2019).

This time, the 2022 PISA results revealed that the average results were about the same as those in 2018, and there were no significant changes in the students' scores in science. Nonetheless, Filipino students scored less than the OECD average. For context, the results were cautiously interpreted due to exceptional circumstances throughout this period of the Coronavirus Disease or COVID-19 pandemic (OECD, 2023).

Another international assessment of the International Association for the Evaluation of Education Achievement, the 2019 edition of Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS), divulged that the Philippines scored 297 in Mathematics and 249 in Science, placing lowest among 58 nations. Furthermore, according to this assessment in science, only 1% belong to the high benchmark (550 score), while about 6% belong to the intermediate benchmark (475 score), and 13% are in the low benchmark (400 score). Overall, this proposes that Filipino students need more understanding of scientific concepts and more knowledge of foundational science facts.

These reports are essential to reveal critical details in resolving the issues in the Philippines and the regional and local settings. Various factors contribute to these concerns, particularly in science education. These include the distribution of content topics and competencies in the K to 12 science curriculum compared to international standards, teachers' personalities, instructional methods, resources, and the overall learning environment. Insufficient instructional resources, mainly teaching aids and materials, cause significant challenges in teaching science effectively.

Many issues, notably the lack of educational resources and teaching methods in line with the learning goals outlined by the DepEd, impact scientific education today. Some science topics and principles are challenging for teachers since few pertinent, responsive, research-based resources are available (Rogoyan & Dollete, 2019).

In cases of learning loss, teachers are fully responsible for select students' progress. A strategic intervention material (SIM) is used in remedial sessions to focus on developing the learner's least learned competencies (LLCs). A SIM combined with teachers' skills in technology, creativity, and resourcefulness helps students acquire competency-based skills that they would not have achieved in a regular classroom setting (Bundang & Parangat, 2022). Because of the COVID-19 pandemic, the widespread use and studies of SIMs increased to intervene with the learning gaps during distance learning.

In the Philippines, SIMs officially started when DepEd introduced them through DepEd Memorandum No. 117 s.2005 Training Workshop on Strategic Interventions for Successful Learning. The administration of adequate instructional interventions through extra lessons for learners below expected grades was further emphasized in DepEd Order 08 s.2015 Policy Guidelines on Classroom Assessment for the K to 12 Basic Education Program.

A SIM reduces the LLCs and improves students' performance (Hulipas, 2019). It includes a variety of activities and resources and essential interactive discussions that allow

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World Education Connect Multidisciplinary e-Publication

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Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

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National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

students to study and explore independently while being designed to help students learn and master the material (Arpilleda, 2021; Zabala, 2023).

Dacumos (2016) studied that teachers' perspectives on SIM integration vary, ranging from abridging complex concepts to using SIM as a reteaching tool. They take a dynamic approach to SIM, empowering students to construct their knowledge. Utilizing SIM encourages independent learning and memory improvement, sparks critical thinking, and allows students to comprehend scientific ideas actively. On another note, Gabucan and Sanchez (2021) suggested that SIM can be used in remedial and regular settings and that all competencies are covered in the curriculum.

Lastly, according to the study by Dumape (2022), SIMs can improve the process of teaching and learning. They have the potential to change conventional classroom procedures and address certain pedagogical difficulties that challenge instructors' beliefs, practices, and tactics. However, there is no way to quantify the potential influence of SIM-assisted instruction on teaching and learning. Thus, they are truly significant for the education of learners in this generation, both now and in the future.

On the other hand, SIMs can be used in several subject areas as long as they purposefully accomplish their goal. Several studies have utilized SIMs in teaching science.

Samosa (2021) created a comic cum strategic intervention material (CoSIM) to teach biology concepts on photosynthesis. As a result, students exposed to the CoSIM got higher scores in the post-test, and their attitude towards it was highly positive. Likewise, students' academic performance was linked with a significant positive relationship towards using CoSIM.

Additionally, Sumandal and De Gracia (2023) developed an electronic SIM (e-SIM) for teaching General Biology to Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) students and assessed its content, instructional, and technical quality through pre-test and post-test results. This study concluded that there had been a significant improvement in students' performance using the e-SIM, which can be further evaluated and improved. One activity that helps students understand complex science concepts is manipulation. Therefore, teachers are urged to use their creativity to the fullest to create a successful SIM that will aid students in developing their scientific knowledge (Dandan, 2022).

Meanwhile, Alair (2020) conducted another experimental study on pre-test and post-test design using SIM in Grade 8 Science. The study showed that SIM is more effective than traditional teaching approaches in increasing students' performance levels, particularly in LLCs.

Sinco (2020) developed and used a teacher-made SIM in the least concepts of Science 6 on circulatory, nervous, and respiratory systems and found that using SIMs is an effective intervention. Moreover, students positively perceived using SIMs and found it "enjoyable, interesting, and contributes positive attitude towards learning more concepts in Science." Similar research was conducted to assess the SIM on the LLCs in Science 6 about homogeneous and heterogeneous mixtures, and it was found that the SIM effectively improves students' performance. However, the researchers believe that through SIM, educators and school administrators should be able to preserve and enhance the activities offered, allowing students to pick up new concepts and develop their scientific abilities (Suarez & Casinillo, 2020).

In addition, Arevalo, Janer, and Ricafort's (2023) research produced a contextualized SIM (CSIM) on Physics 8 as an innovative teaching practice during modular distance learning using the ADDIE Model. The CSIM was meant to adapt the lesson to the student's learning

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needs and comprehension levels in a creative, relevant, meaningful, and flexible way. By the name itself, it applied contextualization, putting a lesson into a meaningful and applicable framework based on prior knowledge and actual circumstances.

Meanwhile, Kirk (2015) asserts the use of manipulatives, or models for teaching abstract or challenging information, may be advantageous to students as it gives them an active manner to absorb the material and boosts their interest in science-related subjects. The researcher further concludes that there is a strong indication that the use of manipulatives did help students increase their understanding of difficult topics in chemistry. One thing that students would want to perform to understand the challenging ideas in scientific education is manipulation (Dacumos, 2016).

On the contrary, SIMs can be overwhelming too. In the 2023 National Readership Survey (NRS) of the National Book Development Board of the Philippines, it was revealed that children aged 17 and below find reading tiring even when they believe it has positive effects and importance to play. Furthermore, Ismail (2022) too much text is information overload which results in academic stress and negatively impacts students' psychological and physical well-being. Similarly, Satriani (2020) finds reading difficulties when there is no motivation to read, low reading skills, too much time to read, need to study complex words, too difficult material due to grammatical complexities, and lengthy texts and sentences.

Moreover, SIMs lack differentiated instruction. Renzulli and Reis (2018) define differentiation as adapting to students' learning styles, expressive styles, interests, and talents appropriate to the curriculum. Adding differentiation to SIMs satisfies different learning styles, allows learners to demonstrate learning ways, and creates flexible learning spaces and opportunities. Implementing differentiated instruction includes providing materials of varied difficulty, different types of assistance, and varied grouping methods.

These narratives for reducing cognitive overload, and reading difficulties, and adding differentiated instruction are important to the development of an innovative SIM under this study.

Meanwhile, aside from SIMs, learning intervention materials may come in different forms. Like Tagupa and Arnado's (2023), Motivational Manipulative Learning Materials (MMLM) were developed for the least-learned competencies and concluded that they are 'truly relevant and useful for teaching and learning purposes.

To address these challenges in learning gaps because of the COVID-19 pandemic and alternative learning delivery, DepEd released the nationwide implementation of Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) starting School Year 2022-2023. It is also the national agency's response to the call of SDG 4 for a more resilient education system and continuous mechanisms of educational continuity in times of emergency.

As a result, the purpose of this study was to address the learning gaps in Physics 8's LLCs by developing an innovative SIM, The Science Pyramid, also known as The SciePy.

Statement of the Objectives

This study developed and validated The SciePy, an innovative SIM for the LLCs in Physics 8. Specifically, it pursued the following objectives:

1. To develop the SIM according to the ADDIE Model:
 - 1.1 Analysis;
 - 1.2 Design;
 - 1.3 Development;
 - 1.4 Implementation; and
 - 1.5 Evaluation.

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2. To validate the SIM by:
 - 2.1 Experts:
 - 2.1.1 Content;
 - 2.1.2 Instructional Design;
 - 2.1.3 Technical Design; and
 - 2.1.4 Other Findings.
 - 2.2 Student-users:
 - 2.2.1 Effectiveness.
 - 2.2.1.1 Pre-test and Post-test
3. To draw the implications of the study of using SIM for the LLCs in Physics 8.

Hypothesis of the Study

H₀: There is no significant difference in the student participants' scores on the pre-test and post-test using the developed SIM in Physics 8.

Methods

This study utilized research and development (R&D) as the educational research design. According to Gustiani (2019), the R&D Method has been widely applied and implemented in academic research at all levels of education because of its linearity in developing and validating educational materials. Bulaun (2023) defines an educational product as a response to an academic issue when the product's viability is determined. If the product constructively solves the problem, it will be approved as a supplementary material. Otherwise, until its efficacy is demonstrated, it will be evaluated, adjusted, and enhanced. The product in this study was the innovative SIM, The Science Pyramid or The SciePy, which is developmental and helps realize the LLCs in Physics 8.

Furthermore, R&D is the most suitable research design in this matter because the SIM was methodologically developed to enhance a pool of information in understanding the problem and finding new uses for that existing knowledge. OECD (2018) enumerated that an R&D material or activity should be novel, creative, uncertain, systematic, transferable, and/or reproducible. R&D encompasses three types such as basic research, applied research, and experimental development, to which this study was based on underlying foundations of phenomena and observable facts, directed objectives, and drawing knowledge to produce new products or processes.

Specifically, using the principles of R&D, this study utilized the ADDIE model. It is one of the most commonly used models in instructional design to help create a successful design (Aldoobie, 2015). It is also a method and framework for designing and developing educational learning materials (Luzano, 2020).

Locale of the Study

The study was conducted at Ayala High School, a public secondary school in Rice Village, Ayala, Magalang, in Pampanga, Philippines.

Sampling Design

The study used a purposive sampling technique to select participants. To effectively address the study objective and questions, this strategic sampling strategy sought "information-rich cases" (Leavy, 2017). When using a purposive sample, the researcher

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deliberately chose participants based on their familiarity with the populace to obtain information that interests them and may or may not be intended to be representative (Mackey & Gass, 2017). It is also called purposeful sampling since it assumes that the researcher wishes to learn as much as possible and must choose a sample that will allow for the most significant amount of understanding and discovery (Merriam & Tisdell, 2017).

Participants of the Study

The participants of this study were divided into two groups: experts and students:

Expert Validators

This study involved six experts who validated the developed innovative SIM and came from four different DepEd public secondary schools in Magalang, Pampanga namely Ayala High School (2), Dolores National High School (1), Tinajero National High School – Annex (2), and Rodolfo V. Feliciano Memorial High School (1). They are DepEd teachers having seven (2), nine (1), 12 (1), 16 (1), and 25 (1) years in service; bachelor degree graduate of Bachelor of Science in Biology (1), and Bachelor of Secondary Education major in General Science (5); master's degree graduate of Master of Arts in Education major in General Science (3), Educational Management (2), and Physical Science (1); and holding current positions as Teacher III (3) and Master Teacher I (3). Meanwhile, the subjects they handle are Physical Science in SHS (2), and Science 8 (4) while three also handle Science 9 and one with Earth and Life Science at the same time.

Overall, the chosen experts were qualified because of having more than five years in service, having earned bachelor's and master's degrees relevant to science education, having handled science-related subjects, and having earned at least a Teacher III position. These criteria were set and met to prove the authenticity of their role in assessing the material.

The expert validators were selected regardless of age, sex, and socioeconomic status. A curriculum vitae was requested from them to prove their qualifications.

Student Participants

Thirty-one (31) student participants were purposively selected from Grade 8 Amber, Amethyst, Ametrine, and Azurite. They obtained grades of 75 to 79, which belonged to the "Fairly Satisfactory" passing mark in Science 8 of the 1st Quarter S. Y. 2023-2024. It is assumed that these students fit the criteria of having trouble grasping competencies, hence resulting in the least mastery. These participants took pre-tests, navigated and learned through the crafted innovative SIM, and took post-tests. They were chosen regardless of their age, sex, and socio-economic status.

Research Instruments

The study utilized the following instruments:

1. The adopted LRMSD Evaluation Rating Sheet for Manipulatives from DepEd's Guidelines and Processes for LRMSD Assessment & Evaluation in 2009 was used for the evaluation phase. This instrument was used for the sole intention of evaluating the SIM and was not meant for approval and reproduction. However, it is noteworthy that the material is said to have potentially qualified the DepEd criteria on instructional materials using this instrument.

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Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

2. Pre-test and post-test questionnaires were crafted by the researcher and validated by experts before administration. It contains a 50-item multiple choice type of test with four choices and follows the TOS with seven hours of teaching across the seven LLCs identified during the 1st Quarter of S. Y. 2023-2024 in Science 8.

Results and Discussions

Development of The SciePy

The SciePy's Inspiration

The inspiration for The SciePy's geometric shape was drawn from the researcher's locale which is situated at the foothills of Mt. Arayat. A pyramid was used to resemble a mountain and to symbolize scientific knowledge to be drawn out of mystery and curiosity – just like how real-life pyramids are studied. Therefore, the SIM was named 'The Science Pyramid' or The SciePy.

The SciePy as an Innovative SIM

The design of The SciePy was based on a rotating three-dimensional square pyramid. It consisted of four lateral faces, a base, a stem, and an apex. Each lateral face has a sliding panel where Title or Teaser Cards can be inserted; can be opened to reveal the learning activities inside; and when opened, contains another panel where Guide Cards can be slid and a space for enclosed learning activities.

As a SIM, its parts were modified from the existing common formats of print and non-print SIMs. However, it retained the Title Card, Guide Card, and Activity Card yet removed the Enrichment Card, Answer Card, and Reference Card. Instead, the Title Card can also be turned into a Teaser Card to remove repetitiveness but add significant details to the content and competencies at hand. The Activity Card already involves all relative learning activities with varying difficulty, hence, the Enrichment Card was removed. Since it is meant to be used for face-to-face learning modality, the Answer Card was removed to pave the way for facilitator and learner interaction in giving feedback and assessing formative learning. Likewise, Assessment Card was removed but pre-tests and post-tests were given in the forms of a ZipGrade sheet and a test questionnaire before and after each session. The Reference Card also became insignificant since it does not matter to learners anyway. However, references can be found in the facilitator's Lesson Exemplar. Lastly, the Summary Card was added to contain all concepts learned, their application, and their value to real life.

The SciePy's Pedagogical Foundations

As for its pedagogical perspective, The SciePy's mechanism was intended to support constructivism, cognitive theory, learning and development theory, and experiential learning. It was intended for the learners to dominate the construction of learning with their peers while guided by the facilitator. The design of instruction must be secured with educational theories that offer a framework for creating dependable, consistent, enticing, and successful training (Khalil & Elkhider, 2016).

The foundation of The SciePy is anchored in constructivism. With this paradigm, students actively create their view of the world by drawing from their past experiences and knowledge. Students can build an understanding of Physics concepts since the SIM

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promotes active involvement and participation through its interactive features and practical exercises. According to Golder (2018), constructivism makes learners enjoy learning when actively involved, concentrates on learning how to think and understand, stimulates and engages students through real-world contextual activities, and promotes social and communication skills by creating a classroom environment that emphasizes collaboration and exchange of ideas, and develops students' abilities to express knowledge.

Another foundational theory of The SciePy is the cognitive load theory. According to this theory, which focuses on how the human cognitive system processes information, learners' capacity to process new knowledge is constrained (Asma & Dallel, 2020). Hence, The SciePy presents Physics ideas in an organized and scaffolded way to manage cognitive load efficiently. The progressively increasing complexity of each face of the pyramid enables students to build on their prior knowledge without using excessive cognitive capacity.

Thirdly, The SciePy supports the learning and development theory. According to the Medical College of Wisconsin (2022), Psychologist Lev Vygotsky's theory proposes learning as a process of acquiring knowledge and problem-solving strategies through social interactions that further verifies gained knowledge. Furthermore, this theory involves the Zone of Proximal Development, which tells that learners can do some chores independently yet require assistance with things they cannot do. Hence, The SciePy contains activities that engage learners to collaborate with their peers with appropriate guidance from the researcher during the sessions.

In addition, experiential learning is strengthened in The SciePy. Bartle (2015) states that experiential learning allows participants to observe, examine, and reflect on what they have performed before, critically and consciously linking their experiences to theory or past experiences. Likewise, it is defined as a continual process in which theory and practice are conceptualized and reconceptualized, each spiral strengthening a student's understanding. In The SciePy, learners will experience hands-on learning and a personalized approach facilitated by the researcher.

Lastly, The SciePy is incorporated to give active and immediate feedback for effective learning. Feedback provides an opportunity to close a gap between present competency and the one required by the facilitator or activity (Ahea et al., 2016).

The SciePy's Mechanisms

Each lateral face of the pyramid also represents four phases in the learning session anchored in the 7Es of Learning as reflected in the Lesson Exemplar. This cycle involves seven learning parts Elicit, Engage, Explore, Elaborate, Explain, Extend, and Evaluate.

Phase I covers the Elicit and Engage parts by taking the pre-test and pre-activity for 10 to 15 minutes. This phase invites learners to activate prior knowledge and their attention to the current session. Phase II is equal to the Explore portion where students perform an activity that builds and helps construct new knowledge and skills that may take at least 30 minutes. Phase III, which is anchored with Elaborate, solidifies learners' acquired knowledge and skills by executing another activity. Lastly, Phase IV summarizes and conveys the application of the knowledge and skills in real-life scenarios which are embedded in the Explain and Extend parts. It also concludes their session by receiving a chest reward and partaking in the post-test as in the Evaluate part. The Extend and Evaluate parts were interchanged in this manner to accommodate the complete strategy of The SciePy.

Rahman and Chavhan (2022) outlined the advantages of using the 7Es model in an effective instructional approach for teaching-learning such as aiding in a deeper

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understanding of concepts, making the learning efficient, promoting transfer of learning, stimulating intrinsic motivation to learn, generating confidence and self-esteem, developing thinking skills, developing communication and social skills, and basis for developing instructional materials.

Nonetheless, the 7Es model is commonly used for science teaching strategy in the study's locale which was necessary during the implementation.

Hence, in designing learning activities, The SciePy must support numeracy, literacy, and basic science process skills. This is because DepEd is keen to improve the numeracy and literacy of learners through its NLRP in the MATATAG Curriculum (DepEd, 2023). Basic science process skills are observing, communicating, classifying, measuring metrically, inferring, and predicting. These are important because they can be used by students to study science independently, to easily understand complex concepts with them, to refute mistakes in new data, and to solve problems and communicate the solution to others (Maison et. al., 2019).

After the ideation relative to The SciePy's design, all ideas were transcribed to a tangible object. Hence, the base SIM design was materialized using plywood panels supported by a sturdy metal tubular stem and solid wood circular base. All these were built together using wood glue, nails, and screws while the lateral faces were attached with hinges at the bottom and push lock on top. The entire wooden body was puttied to remove the risk of getting wood splinters. Meanwhile, the slide layouts were made through Canva and printed in specialty papers.

Colors were critically thought to continuously engage learning and help learners easily navigate the SIM. Thus, every lateral face of the pyramid was painted with solid colors to indicate specific phases accordingly: Phase I – green, Phase II – yellow, Phase III – blue, and Phase IV – red, Meanwhile, the apex was painted orange. Even the slide attachments were colored correspondingly with the lateral faces.

Amarin and Al-saleh (2020) recommend designing instructional aids with colors that promote comfort and inspire a good learning environment like bright ones to stimulate and motivate learning.

Finally, the researcher was able to produce seven The SciePy models and seven sets of learning activities. The cost for each model was estimated at around 1,750 Philippine pesos although this study does not explore its cost-effectiveness.

The researcher also produced The SciePy Handbook: A User's Guide to help future users in utilizing the material. This contains similar development details from this study, detailed instructions on usage, intended audience and objectives, sample activities, safety precautions, and maintenance and care.

Validation of The SciePy

In terms of Factor A: Content, the expert validators rated the SIM as 'PASSED' with an average score of 38.83 out of 40 points. Eight indicators were rated 4.00 while the other two were rated differently. Indicator 8 "Typographic layout/design facilitates understanding of concepts presented" was rated 3.00 or Satisfactory while Indicator 9 "The size of the material is appropriate for use in school" was rated 3.84 or Very Satisfactory. This suggests that improvements are needed in the layout, design, and size of the SIM. As for its typography, experts suggest further increasing the font size of the texts. While the SIM's size is relatively big already, one expert suggested a much bigger size to be used by the facilitator in front of the class. However, the SIM is not meant to be presented in front of the class but to be used

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World Education Connect

Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue VII (July 2024), p.21-38 International

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

collaboratively by students within a small group. Table 1 summarizes the expert-validators' evaluation in terms of content.

Table 1

Expert-validators' Evaluation in Terms of Factor A (Content)

Indicators	Average Score	Descriptive Rating
1. Content reinforces, enriches, and/or leads to the mastery of certain learning competencies for the level and subject it was intended.	4.00	VS
2. Material has the potential to arouse the interest of the target users.	4.00	VS
3. The facts are accurate.	4.00	VS
4. The information provided is up-to-date.	4.00	VS
5. Visuals are relevant to the text.	4.00	VS
6. Visuals are suitable to the age level and interests of the target user.	4.00	VS
7. Visuals are clear and adequately convey the message of the subject or topic.	4.00	VS
8. Typographic layout/design facilitates understanding of concepts presented.	3.00	S
9. The size of the material is appropriate for use in school.	3.83	VS
10. The material is easy to use and durable.	4.00	VS
Total Score	38.83	PASSED

Legend: 3.26-4.00 = Very Satisfactory (VS) *Total Points* ≥30
 points = Passed

2.56-3.25 = Satisfactory (S)

1.76-2.55 = Poor (P)

1.00-1.75 = Not Satisfactory (NS)

Factor B determines the overall acceptability of the developed material. If any error was found, it would automatically be rejected or marked failed. In the case of this study, The SciePy was found to be error-free as rated by the experts with an average score of 16 out of 16 points. Hence, the material 'PASSED' this factor. The summary of the experts' scores in terms of Factor B (Other Findings) is presented in Table 2.

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Table 2

Expert-validators' Evaluation in Terms of Factor B (Other Findings)

Indicators	Average Score	Descriptive Rating
1. Conceptual errors.	4.00	Not Present
2. Factual errors.	4.00	Not Present
3. Grammatical and/or typographical errors.	4.00	Not Present
4. Other errors (i.e., computational errors, obsolete information, errors in the visuals, etc.).	4.00	Not Present
Total Score	16.00	PASSED

Legend: 3.26-4.00 = Not Present Total Points ≥ 16
points = Passed

2.56-3.25 = Present but with very minor & must be fixed

1.76-2.55 = Present & requires major redevelopment

1.00-1.75 = Poor

Lastly, expert-validators evaluated The SciePy in terms of Factor C which is an additional requirement for manipulative materials according to instructional and technical designs. As a result, experts marked the SIM as 'PASSED' with an average score of 23.83 out of 24 points. Notably, all indicators were rated 4.00 except for Indicator 4 "Manipulative is safe to use" which was rated 3.83. One expert worried about the opening-closing mechanism of the manipulative SIM because some learners might get hurt or their hands get crushed by the lateral faces. Table 3 summarizes the expert validators' evaluation in terms of instructional and technical designs for manipulative materials.

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Table 3

*Expert-validators' Evaluation in Terms of Factor C
(Additional Requirements for Manipulative)*

Indicators	Average Score	Descriptive Rating
<i>Instructional Design</i>		
1. Adequate support material is provided.	4.00	VS
2. Activities are summarised; extension activities are provided.	4.00	VS
3. Suggested activities support innovative pedagogy.	4.00	VS
<i>Technical Design</i>		
4. Manipulative is safe to use.	3.83	VS
5. The size and composition of the manipulative are appropriate for the intended audience.	4.00	VS
6. Suggested manual tasks within the activities are compatible with the motor skills of the intended users	4.00	VS
Total Score	23.83	PASSED

Legend: 3.26-4.00 = Very Satisfactory (VS) Total Points ≥ 18
 points = Passed
 2.56-3.25 = Satisfactory (S)
 1.76-2.55 = Poor (P)
 1.00-1.75 = Not Satisfactory (NS)

After the implementation phase, the student participants were administered with post-test and their scores were analyzed. Table 4 recaps the differences between their pre-test and post-test scores using SPSS software. The analysis reveals a significant improvement in scores from the pre-test to the post-test. The mean post-test score (35.1) is substantially higher than the mean pre-test score (20.3), with a significant mean difference of -14.7. The highly significant p-value (< 0.001) indicates strong evidence against the null hypothesis, confirming that the increase in scores is not due to random chance but likely due to an effective intervention or learning period between the pre-test and post-test assessments. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected.

The post-test scores of student participants improved significantly using the innovative SIM. Therefore, it can be inferred that the innovative SIM is effective to be used for intervention sessions for the select LLCs in Physics 8. This discovery aligns with several studies indicating that SIMs have the potential to improve students' performance (Contreras, 2018; Hulipas, 2019; Alair, 2020; and Sumandal & De Gracia, 2023), particularly as manipulative SIMs (Kirk, 2015; and Tagupa & Arnado, 2023).

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Table 4

Paired Sample T-test of Pre-test & Post-test Results

			statistic	df	p	Mean difference	SE difference
Pre-test	Post-test	Student's t	-14.8	30.0	< .001	-14.7	0.997

Note: $H_a \mu_{\text{Measure 1}} - \mu_{\text{Measure 2}} \neq 0$

Descriptives						
	N	Mean	Median	SD	SE	
Pre-test	31	20.3	21	4.79	0.861	
Post-test	31	35.1	33	4.77	0.856	

Implications of the Study in Science Education

With the very satisfactory remarks in experts' evaluation and positive increase in students' test results, the study indicates innovative and manipulative SIM has the potential to boost students' understanding and performance in the LLCs in Physics 8. Likewise, the material consistently delivers substantial benefits across all student participants. With the return of face-to-face learning modalities, learners may have a different approach to learning complex competencies in the curriculum. Meanwhile, teachers are encouraged to adopt and develop the innovative SIM further and foster a culture of continuous innovation but with the assurance that it certainly addresses learning difficulties in Physics 8.

The result of this study has great implications for teaching Physics to Grade 8 students, especially those who are lagging. The innovative SIM can be used as a supplementary material for intervention sessions while considering also the changes that took place in utilizing it. The success of this study can influence the integration of similar intervention materials in the current K to 12 curriculum in the Philippines through educational policies, teachers' professional development, and R&D.

Limitations of the Study

The findings of the study have to be seen in light of some limitations. First, it was guided by the ADDIE model. Second, validation of the material was conducted by only six teaching staff who met the set qualifications, utilizing the LRMDs rating sheet to evaluate content, errors, and manipulative designs. Meanwhile, 31 students participated in this study. Third, The SciePy was assessed using the pre-test and post-test results from selected participants. Consequently, the study does not consider other factors that might have influenced the significant increase in test results, such as learning activities, environment, and strategies. Lastly, the study does not disclose details on the step-by-step development of the SIM, acceptability, user satisfaction, and user perception.

Recommendations

The development of innovative instructional materials, such as SIMs, requires an instructional design model to have a solid structure and procedure for the intended output

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and outcome. Future researchers may utilize other instructional design models than the ADDIE Model like Merrill's Principles of Instruction, Gagne's Nine Events of Instructions, Dick and Carey Model, and Kemp Design Model, or innovative processes such as design thinking and agile instructional design approach. They are recommended to employ a different teaching strategy other than the 7Es of learning.

Reproducing The SciePy could be costly. Future researchers and users may intend to use indigenous and/or recyclable materials. For the panels and overall structure, polyvinyl chloride (PVC or vinyl) boards, bamboo boards, and any weightless yet durable lumber can be utilized instead. Re-inventing the materials used could lead to a cost-effective material and could potentially improve the dimensions and features of the current SIM.

Further validation of The SciePy requires studies in bigger sample sizes. Future studies may involve more expert-validators and the inclusion of educational technologists or instructional designers and specialists other than science teachers in the field. Likewise, these may also target a larger sample with various backgrounds and academic performance levels or a comparison between traditional teaching with the ones integrated with this innovative SIM and even with other types of instructional materials. Otherwise, The SciePy may be used in a completely different locale. Also, it may be applied within the whole quarter with the complete necessary competencies in the new MATATAG Curriculum of DepEd to further test its efficacy.

References

- Ahea, M. A. B., Ahea, R. K., & Rahman, I. (2016). *The Value and Effectiveness of Feedback in Improving Students' Learning and Professionalizing Teaching in Higher Education*. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 7(16)
- Alair, G. P. (2020). *Strategic Intervention Materials: Their Effects on the Academic Performance in Science of the Grade-8 Students of Bai Saripinang National High School*. *International Journal of Scientific Engineering and Applied Science*, 6(12)
- Aldoobie, N. (2015). *ADDIE Model*. *American International Journal of Contemporary Research*, 5(6)
- Amarin, N. & Al-saleh, A. (2020). *The Effect of Color Use in Designing Instructional Aids on Learners' Academic Performance*. *Journal of E-Learning and Knowledge Society*, 16(2) 42-50.
- Arevalo, C. M. E., Janer, S. S., & Ricafort, J. D. (2023). *Development of Contextualized Strategic Intervention Materials for Grade-8 Physics*. *United International Journal for Research & Technology*, 4(07) 114-118
- Arpilleda, A. J. (2021). *Strategic intervention material: A tool in enhancing grade nine students' mathematical performance*. *International Journal of Research Studies in Education*, 10(5). DOI: 10.5861/ijrse.2021.5051
- Asma, H. & Dallel, S. (2020). *Cognitive Load Theory and its Relation to Instructional Design: Perspectives of Some Algerian University Teachers*. *Arab World English Journal (AWEJ)*, 11(4) 110-127. DOI: <https://dx.doi.org/10.24093/awej/vol11no4.8>
- Ban, J. C., Kim, S. & Shin, M. (2022) *Supporting Lagging Students and Learning for All: Applying the Diagnose-and-Supplement System of Basic Skills in the Republic of Korea*. *Asian Development Bank*. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.22617/SPR210528>

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- Bartle, E. (2015). *Experiential Learning: An Overview*. Institute for Teaching and Learning Innovation. The University of Queensland, Australia.
- Bernardo, A. B. I., Ordell II, M. O., Calleja, M. O., Teves, J. M. M., Yap, S. A., & Chua, U. C. (2023). *Profiling low-proficiency science students in the Philippines using machine learning*. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*, 10:192. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-023-01705-y>
- Bulaun, C. M. P. (2023). *Development and Validation of an Interactive e-Book in Physics 9*. 23. Tarlac State University
- Bundang, M. & Parangat, K. B. (2022). *Teacher-Made Strategic Intervention Materials for Students with Learning Difficulties in Mathematics 8 in the Philippines*. *Universe International Journal of Interdisciplinary Research*, 10(2). <https://www.doisds.org/doi/10.2022-25185368/UIJIR>
- Contreras, S. J. (2018). *Utilization of Manipulative and Interactive Strategic Intervention Material (MI-SIM) in Chemistry 9*. *Asian Society of Teachers for Research, Inc. Research Journal*, 2(0)
- Dacumos, L. P. N. (2016) *Perspective of Secondary Teachers in the Utilization of Science Strategic Intervention Material (SIM) in Increasing Learning Proficiency of Students in Science Education*. *AsTEN Journal of Teacher Education*, 1(2)
- Dandan, K. B. V. (2022). *E-SIM (Electronic Strategic Intervention Material) in Science 9: An Aid to Improve Online Learning Performance*. *International Journal of Research Publications*, 103(1) p. 288-298 doi.org/10.47119/IJRPQ01031620223428
- Department of Education (2005). *DepEd Memorandum No. 117 s. 2005 Training Workshop on Strategic Interventions for Successful Learning*
- Department of Education (2015). *DepEd Order No. 8 s. 2015 Policy Guidelines on Classroom Assessment for the K to 12 Basic Education Program*
- Department of Education (2016). *Kto12 Curriculum Guide Science* https://www.deped.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2019/01/Science_CG_with-tagged-sci-equipment_revised.pdf
- Department of Education (2019). *DepEd Order No. 021 s. 2019: Policy Guidelines on the Kto12 Basic Education Program*
- Department of Education (2023). *DepEd Memorandum No. 013 s. 2023 Adoption of the National Learning Recovery Program in the Department of Education*
- Department of Education (2023). *DepEd Memorandum No. 054 s. 2023 Pilot Implementation of the MATATAG Curriculum*
- Department of Education (2023). *MATATAG Curriculum Science 3-10*
- Dumape, J. L. (2022). *Utilization of Strategic Intervention Material (SIM) In Teaching Grammar among Grade 10 Students*. *International Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities Invention* 9(08), 7113-7125. DOI: 10.18535/ijsshi/v9i08.01
- Gabucan, J. R. & Sanchez, J. M. P. (2021). *Strategic intervention material (SIM)-based instruction in teaching global warming in 9th-grade science*. *Formatif: Jurnal Ilmiah Pendidikan MIPA*, 11(1): 15-24. <http://dx.doi.org/10.30998/formatif.v11i1.6448>
- Golder, J. (2018). *Constructivism: A Paradigm for Teaching and Learning*. *International Journal of Research and Analytical Reviews*, 5(3)
- Gustiani, S. (2019). *Research & Development (R&D) Method as a Model Design in Educational Research and Its Alternatives*. *Holistics Journal*, 11(2)

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- Hulipas, R. B. (2019) *Development and Validation of Modular Strategic Intervention Material in Teaching Physics*, 42, 46-47, Tarlac State University
- International Association for the Evaluation of Education Achievement (2019). *TIMSS 2019 International Results in Mathematics and Science*
- Ismail, M. R. (2022). *The Impact of the Academic Overload on Students' Well Being Secondary Schools In South Lebanon*. *International Journal of Education, Technology and Science*, 2(2) 181-212.
- Iwuanyanwu, P. N. (2019). *What We Teach in Science, and What Learners Learn: A Gap that Needs Bridging*. *Pedagogical Research*, 4(2), em0032. <https://doi.org/10.29333/pr/5780>
- Khalil, M. K. & Elkhider, I. A. (2016). *Applying learning theories and instructional design models for effective instruction*. The American Physiological Society. doi:10.1152/advan.00138.2015.
- Kirk, J. (2015). *Using Manipulatives in the Chemistry Classroom as a Tool to Increase the Understanding and Knowledge of the Law of Conservation of Matter*. Education Masters. Paper 305
- Leavy, P. (2017). *Research Design Quantitative, Qualitative, Mixed Methods, Arts-Based, and Community-Based Participatory Research Approaches*. The Guilford Press, 79
- Lee, S. M. (2018). *Innovation: from small "i" to large "I."* *International Journal of Quality Innovation*, 8(2), 1-10. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40887-018-0022-4>
- Luzano, J. F. P. (2020). *Development and Validation of Strategic Intervention Materials (SIMs) of the Selected Topics in Trigonometry of Precalculus Discipline in Senior High School*. *Journal of Mathematics and Statistics Studies*, DOI: 10.32996/ijllt.2020.1.2.3
- Mackey, A. & Gass, S. M. (2016). *Second Language Research: Methodology and Design (2nd Ed)*. Routledge, 175
- Maison, Darmaji, Astalini, Kurniawan, D. A., & Indrawati, P. S. (2019). *Science Process Skills and Motivation*. *Humanities & Social Sciences Reviews*, 7(5), 48-56. doi:10.18510/hssr.2019.756
- Medical College of Wisconsin (2022). *Sociocultural Theory of Cognitive Development: A Guide to Vygotsky's Theory of Learning*
- Merriam, S. B. & Tisdell, E. J. (2016). *Qualitative Research: A Guide to Design & Implementation (4th Ed)*. Jossey-Bass, 96
- Official Gazette of the Philippines (n.d.). *What is Kto12 Program?* <https://www.officialgazette.gov.ph/k-12/>
- Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (2014). *Equity and Quality in Education: Supporting Disadvantaged Students and Schools*. OECD Publishing. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1787/9789264130852-en>
- Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (2018) *Definitions of Research and Development: An Annotated Compilation of Official Sources*
- Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (2019). *Programme for International Student Assessment results from PISA 2018*. https://www.oecd.org/pisa/publications/PISA2018_CN_PHL.pdf.
- Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (2023). *PISA 2022 Results (Volume I): The State of Learning and Equity in Education*. PISA, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/53f23881-en>

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- Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (2023). *PISA 2022 Results (Volume II): Learning During – and From Disruption*. PISA, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/a97db61c-en>
- Rahman, S. & Chavhan, R. (2022). *7E Model: An Effective Instructional Approach for Teaching Learning*. EPRA International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research, 8(1) 339-345. DOI: 10.36713/epra2013
- Samosa, R. C. (2021). *COSIM (Comics Cum SIM): An innovative material in teaching biology*. European Journal of Research Development and Sustainability 2(4),19-28
- Satriani, E. (2018). *Reading Comprehension Difficulties Encountered by English Students of Islamic University of Riau*. Journal of English for Academic, 5(2) DOI: 10.25299/jshmic.2018.vol5(2).1885
- Sinco, M. G. M. (2020). *Strategic Intervention Materials: A Tool in Improving Students' Academic Performance*. International Journal for Research in Applied And Natural Science, 6(5)
- Suarez, M. G. & Casinillo, L. F. (2020). *Effect of strategic intervention material (SIM) on academic performance: evidence from students of science VI*. Review of Socio-Economic Research and Development Studies, 4(1) 20-32
- Sumandal, A. H. & De Gracia, R. S. (2023). *Utilization of Electronic – Strategic Intervention Material (E-SIM) in Teaching General Biology for STEM Students*. International Journal of Research Publication and Reviews 4(10) doi.org/10.55248/gengpi.4.1023.102621
- Tagupa, E. & Arnado, A. (2023). *Development and Validation of Motivational Manipulative Learning Materials (MMLMs) for the Least-Learned Competencies of Grade 9 Trigonometry*. International Journal of Membrane Science and Technology, 10(2) 1002-1022
- Yoldere, H. M., Adamu, M., & Inuwa, I. A. (2018) *The Roles of Science Teachers in Promoting Science Education for Sustainable Development in the North Eastern Nigeria*. International Journal of Educational Research and Management Technology, 3(1) 82-90.
- Zabala, O. E. (2023). *Strategic Intervention Material (SIM) on Senior High School Student Learning in Stocks and Bonds*. American Journal of Education and Technology, 2(4), 24-29 <https://doi.org/10.54536/ajet.v2i4.2182>
- Zalun, J. (2023). *The Teachers' Utilization of the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCS) and its Relation to the Learning Development of Grade Six Pupils in a Public School in the Philippines: Basis for a Proposed Program*. International Journal of Multidisciplinary: Applied Business and Education Research 4(6) 1888-1903. <http://dx.doi.org/10.11594/ijmaber.04.06.15>

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.12753622

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